

Conductance Studies of Alkali Metal Chlorides and Bromides in Aqueous Binary Mixtures of Tetrahydrofuran at 25°

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Precise conductance measurements are reported for alkali metal chlorides and bromides, MX ($M^+ = \text{Li, Na, K, Rb and Cs}$; $X^- = \text{Cl and Br}$) in tetrahydrofuran (THF) + water mixtures at 25°. The limiting molar conductivity (Λ°) the association constant (K_A) and association distance (R) in the solvent mixtures have been evaluated using the Fuoss conductance equation (1978). The analysis of data indicates that the electrolytes are almost unassociated at 0.059 mole fraction of THF, whereas at 0.143, 0.273 and 0.500 mole fraction of THF, the association was very strong. The values for alkali metal cations (anion being the same) are found to be in the order: $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Rb}^+ < \text{Cs}^+$. The results have been explained in terms of ion-solvent interactions and structural changes in the mixed solvents.

Studies on ionic solvation of alkali metal ions in solvents of low permittivity are very few. Such studies have been assumed importance because of their applications in modern technology¹. Tetrahydrofuran (THF), a solvent of low permittivity ($\epsilon = 7.58$), has also been found its probability of applications in high energy batteries and organic syntheses as manifested from the physicochemical studies in this medium^{2,3}. Renard and Justice⁴ studied the conductances of CsCl in THF+water mixtures to reveal the nature of ionic association and mobility of ions in this mixed solvent system. In the present communication, an attempt has been made to ascertain the complete nature of solute-solvent interactions of alkali metal salts (chlorides as well as bromides) in THF+H₂O mixtures through the measurements of their conductances.

Results and Discussion

The solvent properties of THF+H₂O mixtures are given in Table 1, where ϵ is the dielectric constant, d_0 the density (g cm^{-3}), η_0 the viscosity (cP), L_0 the specific conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), W the weight percent of THF in the aqueous mixtures and X_2 the corresponding mole fraction. Dielectric constants of solvent mixtures were obtained by extrapolation of ϵ versus $W\%$ plots, the original values were taken from the work of Renard and Justice⁴. The equivalent conductance at infinite dilution (Λ°) and the association constant (K_A) were calculated using the Fuoss conductance equation⁵,

$$\Lambda = P[\Lambda^\circ(1 + RX) + EL] \quad (1)$$

$$P = [1 - \alpha(1 - \gamma)] \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma = 1 - K_A c \gamma^2 f^2 \quad (3)$$

$$-\ln f = \beta \kappa / 2(1 + \kappa R) \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = e^2 / DkT \quad (5)$$

where the terms have their usual significance. The parameters K_A and R were obtained from the above equations by finding the values of Λ° and α which minimise

$$\sigma^2 = \sum_j [A_j(\text{cal}) - A_j(\text{obs})]^2 / (n-2) \quad (6)$$

for a sequence of R values. Initial Λ° value for the iteration procedure was taken from Shedlovsky extrapolations of the data.

A scan using unit increment of R values from 4 to 20, however, gave no significant minima in the σ^2 - R curve for CsCl, NaBr, RbBr and CsBr at 0.273 mole fraction of THF, and also for the electrolytes (except LiCl) at 0.500 mole fraction of THF. The computations in these cases were carried out from arbitrarily presetting⁶ of R values at $R = a + d$. Here a is the sum of the crystallographic radii of the ions and d the average distance corresponding to the side of a cell occupied by a solvent molecule. The distance d is given by

$$d (\text{\AA}) = (M/N\rho)^{1/3} = 1.183 (M/\rho)^{1/3} \quad (7)$$

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THF-WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

W %	X_2	ϵ	d_0 g cm^{-3}	$10^2 \eta_0$ cp	$10^6 L_0$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$
0	0	78.54	0.997 07	0.890 3	1.01
20	0.059	57.25	0.986 68	1.490 0	3.20
40	0.143	44.50	0.966 40	1.732 1	2.60
60	0.273	32.00	0.946 00	1.490 4	1.35
80	0.500	19.50	0.915 92	0.923 7	1.18
100	1.000	7.58	0.880 72	0.463 0	0.81

where M is the molecular weight of solvent and ρ is its density. For mixed solvents, M is replaced by the mole fraction average molecular weight (M_{av}) which is given by

$$M_{av} = M_1 M_2 / (W_1 M_2 + W_2 M_1) \quad (8)$$

where W_1 is the weight fraction of the first component of molecular weight M_1 . Though, this is an over simplification which ignores possible selective solvation, it at least provides a self-consistent way to obtain an acceptable value for the parameter when a broad range of R values fit the data. The values of Δ^0 , K_A and R obtained by this procedure are recorded in Table 2.

From Table 1, we see that viscosity (η_0) of the solvent mixture (THF + H₂O) increases rapidly to a maximum at about 0.143 mole fraction or 40 wt% of THF and thereafter decreases. Such characteristic in the viscosity vs composition curve is a manifestation of strong specific interaction⁶ between unlike molecules predominated by hydrogen bonding interaction.

Table 2 shows that Δ^0 values for alkali metal halides increase as the size of the cation increases in any mole fraction of mixed solvent. However, for any particular electrolyte, Δ^0 continuously decreases with the addition of THF and Walden products are found to be different; viscosity of solvent-mixture does not coincide with the observed trend in Δ^0 value.

From Table 2, we also see that Δ^0 values of alkali metal salts of common anion follow the sequence: Li⁺ < Na⁺ < K⁺ < Rb⁺ < Cs⁺. Further, the Δ^0 for the alkali metal bromides are greater than those for the corresponding alkali metal chlorides. For CsCl, the Δ^0 value at 0.500 mole fraction of THF is in close proximity with the value reported by Renard and Justice⁴. The trend of variation of Δ^0 values also indicates the relative actual sizes of these ions as they exist in solution. Thus, the sizes of these cations as they exist in solution, follow the order: Li⁺ > Na⁺ > K⁺ > Rb⁺ > Cs⁺, and for anions, Cl⁻ > Br⁻. This shows that Li⁺ is the most solvated and Cs⁺ is the least one in any mole fraction of THF.

It may be observed from Table 2 that the association constant (K_A) is very low for all the electrolytes at 0.059 mole fraction of THF. This indicates that these salts almost remain unassociated in this composition of the solvent mixtures having high dielectric constant. However, at higher mole fraction of THF ($\epsilon < 57.25$) association occurs in the solvent mixtures (for NaCl, KCl and CsCl ion association takes place above 0.143 mole fraction of THF) and that the K_A values increase with the increase of cationic as well as anionic sizes in all cases (except NaBr at 0.500 mole fraction of THF). Thus we see that CsBr in spite of its greater size, is associated maximum than the other bromides at higher percentages of mixed solvents. D'Aprano and Fuoss⁷ found similar trends for many of the alkali metal halides in dioxane-water mixtures.

The values of Walden products ($\Delta^0\eta_0$) for the studied electrolytes pass through a maximum at about 0.059 mole fraction of THF and then decrease continuously. A representative plot for the alkali

TABLE 2—DERIVED CONDUCTANCE PARAMETERS

X_2	Δ^0	K_A	R	$\Delta^0\eta_0$	σ
Lithium chloride					
0 ^a	115.12 ± 0.01	0.79	5.19	1.025	0.03
0.059	60.88 ± 0.06	1.90 ± 0.06	11.41	0.907	0.06
0.143	48.57 ± 0.08	13.92 ± 0.03	12.83	0.841	0.06
0.273	41.38 ± 0.04	20.60 ± 0.40	16.00	0.617	0.07
0.500	30.40 ± 0.17	102.74 ± 0.50	13.20	0.281	0.19
Sodium chloride					
0 ^a	126.53 ± 0.01	0.81	5.56	1.126	0.02
0.059	80.44 ± 0.023	2.96 ± 0.03	10.66	1.198	0.03
0.143	59.76 ± 0.04	6.32 ± 0.09	11.26	1.035	0.05
0.273	46.01 ± 0.05	25.40 ± 0.61	15.27	0.686	0.05
0.500	39.04 ± 0.49	206.53 ± 0.01	7.14	0.361	0.36
Potassium chloride					
0 ^a	149.90 ± 0.01	0.56	4.65	1.334	0.02
0.059	96.10 ± 0.04	2.69 ± 0.05	5.99	1.432	0.03
0.143	72.18 ± 0.03	9.51 ± 0.06	13.00	1.250	0.03
0.273	53.04 ± 0.05	24.11 ± 0.30	16.50	0.790	0.05
0.500	44.92 ± 0.30	228.55 ± 74.80	7.43	0.415	0.90
Rubidium chloride					
0 ^a	153.64 ± 0.01	0.26	3.35	1.367	0.02
0.059	98.19 ± 0.05	4.67 ± 0.04	11.00	1.463	0.07
0.143	74.61 ± 0.07	12.35 ± 0.16	13.00	1.292	0.07
0.273	55.86 ± 0.04	35.64 ± 0.34	15.44	0.833	0.04
0.500	46.84 ± 0.18	458.73 ± 75.29	7.82	0.432	0.94
Cesium chloride					
0 ^a	153.04 ± 0.02	0.62	3.62	1.362	0.02
0.059	100.42 ± 0.04	4.52 ± 0.03	10.00	1.496	0.05
0.143	75.33 ± 0.05	6.41 ± 0.07	11.00	1.305	0.06
0.273	56.51 ± 0.21	31.19 ± 1.70	7.32	0.842	0.25
0.500	50.89 ± 0.46	649.80 ± 36.29	7.84	0.470	0.29
Lithium bromide					
0 ^b	116.88	—	—	1.040	—
0.059	70.53 ± 0.22	2.89 ± 0.25	6.02	1.051	0.25
0.143	55.35 ± 0.06	14.86 ± 0.19	16.60	0.958	0.06
0.273	48.70 ± 0.04	20.35 ± 0.30	17.70	0.726	0.05
0.500	45.93 ± 1.20	265.79 ± 52.73	7.66	0.424	0.75
Sodium bromide					
0 ^b	128.42	—	—	1.143	—
0.059	88.82 ± 0.10	11.70 ± 0.11	13.50	1.323	0.10
0.143	64.57 ± 0.11	28.32 ± 0.41	19.00	1.118	0.12
0.273	53.33 ± 0.81	120.08 ± 12.00	6.82	0.795	0.65
0.500	50.94 ± 0.69	224.28 ± 27.60	7.30	0.470	0.73
Potassium bromide					
0 ^b	157.77	—	—	1.405	—
0.059	103.35 ± 0.06	2.72 ± 0.04	10.80	1.540	0.07
0.143	75.92 ± 0.08	17.10 ± 0.20	14.20	1.315	0.09
0.273	61.39 ± 0.11	45.87 ± 0.84	19.00	0.915	0.13
0.500	52.26 ± 0.66	440.92 ± 42.10	7.62	0.483	0.62
Rubidium bromide					
0 ^b	156.37	—	—	1.392	—
0.059	105.98 ± 0.06	8.79 ± 0.05	11.60	1.579	0.06
0.143	78.03 ± 0.11	22.59 ± 0.32	13.00	1.352	0.11
0.273	66.56 ± 0.65	90.09 ± 6.36	7.29	0.992	0.64
0.500	54.95 ± 1.03	593.02 ± 71.48	7.77	0.507	0.90
Cesium bromide					
0 ^b	155.51	—	—	1.384	—
0.059	109.41 ± 0.04	6.67 ± 0.03	9.90	1.630	0.04
0.143	79.83 ± 0.08	23.13 ± 0.23	17.30	1.383	0.09
0.273	67.75 ± 0.05	82.58 ± 4.80	7.48	1.010	0.50
0.500	58.54 ± 1.71	1001.53 ± 140.56	7.96	0.541	0.98

^aRef. 9. ^bR. L. KAY and D. F. EVANS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 2325.

metal bromides has been given in Fig. 1. Though the variation of the Walden product with solvent composition is difficult to interpret quantitatively, still its variation with solvent composition can be explained by preferential solvation^{8,9} of alkali metal ions by water and THF molecules respectively. At low mole-fraction of THF, these ions are preferentially solvated by water than THF and the viscosity of the solvent in the vicinity of these ions is lower than that of the bulk solvent (Table 1). Since the bulk viscosity value is used in the calcula-

tion of Walden product, the calculated values of $\Delta^0\eta_0$ are high upto the point corresponding to viscosity maximum of the solvent mixtures and then the values decrease gradually causing a maximum in the Walden product. The decrease in the Walden products after 0.143 mole-fraction of THF indicates the preferential solvation of alkali metal ions (having the same anion) by THF in THF+water mixtures. However, this decrease in large part may be due to the Zwanzig¹⁰ solvent relaxation effect also.

Fig. 1. Variation of Walden products ($\Lambda_0\eta_0$) with compositions of solvent mixtures: (1) LiBr, (2) NaBr, (3) KBr, (4) RbBr and (5) CsBr.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran (Merck) was kept several days over KOH, then refluxed for 24 h and distilled over LiAlH_4 . Its boiling point, density and viscosity compared well with the literature values¹¹. The specific conductance of THF was ca. $0.81 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25°.

Alkali metal salts (Fluka, purum or puriss grade) were purified as described earlier¹². A stock solution for each salt ($\sim 0.1 M$) in the appropriate solvent mixture was prepared (by weight) and the working solutions were obtained by weight dilution. The molar concentration of the solution was calculated from molality and density values. The mixed solvents of THF were prepared by mixing the requisite amounts of THF and water (by weights).

Density and viscosity of solvent mixtures were measured in an Ostwald-Sprengel type pycnometer and suspended-level Ubbelohde viscometer at $25 \pm 0.01^\circ$ with a precision of $\pm 3 \times 10^5 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and 0.05% respectively. A Pye-Unicam PW 9509 conductivity meter was used for measuring conductances at the frequency of 2000 Hz with a dip-type cell of cell constant 0.861 cm^{-1} and having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$. The cell was calibrated with aqueous KCl solutions in the usual way. The measurements were carried out in an oil-bath maintained at $25 \pm 0.005^\circ$. The details of experimental procedure have

been described earlier¹³. Several independent solutions were prepared and runs were performed to ensure the reproducibilities of the results. All data were corrected at 25° with the specific conductance of the solvent. The corrected values were analysed by means of the Fuoss conductance equation⁶.

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